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Supplementary material (A) for: A metric approach to paradigmatic collaboration: case study with Prolog

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Abstract

This supplementary material builds upon foundational research documented in our main study, focusing on the analysis of data generated through a metric specifically designed to assess collaboration across programming paradigms and languages. By standardizing the metric parameters ($\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta, \epsilon, \zeta$ each set to $\frac{1}{6}$), we aimed to minimize parameter influence, allowing for the empirical emergence of collaboration thresholds. These thresholds have been validated and further delineated using hierarchical clustering techniques, providing a robust methodological framework for identifying and understanding effective inter-paradigm collaboration. Additionally, this analysis evaluates collaboration between programming languages, revealing significant variability in collaboration scores and identifying potential thresholds for effective integration. These insights underscore the need for adjustable parameters to tailor the metric for specific research contexts and highlight strategic choices in technology selection for software development. The combined analysis of paradigms and languages enriches our understanding of the complex dynamics of software development environments and provides a comprehensive framework for assessing interoperability.

KEYWORDS: Programming Paradigms, Programming Languages, Metric Standardization, Hierarchical Clustering, Collaboration Thresholds, Software Development Metrics, Interoperability

1 Introduction

This supplementary material extends the foundational work presented in our earlier study by (Vandeloise et al. 2024), which introduced a taxonomy of programming paradigms and their interactions. Here, we delve deeper into specifically designed metrics to evaluate the collaboration among these paradigms and the synergy between distinct programming languages. We have deployed a standardized metric with coefficients $\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta, \epsilon,$ and ζ each set to $\frac{1}{6}$, to examine interactions within 28 programming paradigms. Detailed results of this analysis are documented in datasets accessible on (Vandeloise 2024b).

The analysis has identified configurations conducive to productive interaction among 378 combinations of paradigms, revealing potentially promising alliances and the challenges

of certain associations. This process has also highlighted the need to adjust the metric parameters for increased neutrality, thus offering the possibility to customize weights according to specific user needs. This flexibility enhances the metric’s relevance in various application contexts and supports a critical evaluation of collaboration dynamics in programming.

Data were generated using a Haskell model of the various metrics, with the source code available on (Vandeloise 2024a). Datasets are available in both "Cleaned" and "Raw" formats for paradigms and languages, supporting various analyses and further uses:

- `CollaborationMetric_Languages_Cleaned.csv`
- `CollaborationMetric_Languages_Raw.csv`
- `CollaborationMetric_Paradigms_Cleaned.csv`
- `CollaborationMetric_Paradigms_Raw.csv`

2 Application of the metric and analysis of paradigmatic configurations

2.1 Analysis of the distribution of the MC value between paradigms

Generating and interpreting the density graph

To analyse the distribution of these collaboration scores, a robust methodology was employed, using a representative dataset to generate a density plot. Using the `ggplot2`, `dplyr`, and `readr` libraries in the R statistical environment, we prepared the data by converting the MC into percentages. We then calculated the density of these percentages to create a continuous graph revealing the distribution of collaboration scores. The axes of the graph were defined as follows: the X-axis represents the MC percentages, and the Y-axis shows the estimated probability density for each MC value.

Identification of dips

To discern significant trends, we identified troughs in the distribution, which are the points where the probability density is lowest, indicating less common MC scores among the paradigm pairs. These troughs were marked on the graph by vertical lines, with annotations providing the corresponding MC percentages to aid interpretation. This methodical approach ensures an accurate and thorough interpretation of the collaboration dynamics between the programming paradigms studied.

Prevalence of collaboration scores

Density analysis reveals significant concentrations of collaboration scores, where the peaks on the graph correspond to the most frequently observed values among pairs of programming paradigms. These density peaks reflect predominant collaboration scores and suggest that certain paradigm combinations exhibit remarkably high or low compatibility.

Collaboration clusters

The multimodal distribution, illustrated by the presence of several peaks, indicates the existence of distinct clusters of paradigm pairs differing in their degree of collaboration. This observation is indicative of the heterogeneous nature of paradigm interactions, highlighting the tendency of some pairs to exhibit particular collaborative affinities.

Fig. 1: MC value distribution

Collaboration dynamics

The troughs in the distribution, identified as the lowest points separating the peaks, mark less widespread collaboration scores. These local minima may signal transitions between different collaboration regimes, evoking areas of lower inter-paradigmatic compatibility. These troughs could be interpreted as distinctive thresholds between different "classes" or categories of collaboration.

Variability of inter-paradigmatic interactions

The range of MC values on the percentage axis and the presence of multiple peaks and troughs demonstrate substantial variability in the potential for collaboration between paradigm pairs. This variability can be attributed to the diversity of structural features, inheritances, and computational and behavioural properties inherent in the paradigms under consideration.

2.2 Interpretation of collaboration thresholds

Defining collaboration thresholds

Analysis of the clustering data reveals a marked structuring, characterised by high silhouette scores that indicate significant internal cohesion and external distinction between the groups. The clusters identified stand out as their entities within the dataset. The correlation between MC score distributions and cluster boundaries suggests that MC minima correspond to transitions between different collaboration regimes, which could signal changes in collaboration modalities among programming paradigms and serve as natural thresholds for their demarcation. The accuracy of these boundaries validates the

effectiveness of the hierarchical clustering approach used. Collaboration boundaries were defined by combining the evidence from hierarchical clustering with silhouette scores, which attest to the relevance of the clusters formed. The intersections of the minimum MC values and the strength of the silhouette scores make it possible to categorise the levels of collaboration among the programming paradigms. These boundaries provide a framework for assessing the extent of interactions, from simple associations to more integrated collaborations. Establishing thresholds based on MC sheds light on the nature of inter-paradigmatic interactions, facilitating the identification of paradigms that exhibit increased synergy or require strengthening of their collaboration. The heterogeneous distribution of MC scores highlights the impact of paradigms' intrinsic characteristics on their ability to collaborate. This analysis enriches our understanding of the interoperability of programming paradigms and provides a basis for future studies aimed at improving inter-paradigm collaboration.

Fig. 2: Clustering for MC values

2.3 Analysis of the distribution of the MC value between languages

Methodology for analysing collaboration scores

In this analysis, we adopted a methodical approach to evaluate collaboration between programming languages through the analysis of collaboration scores. The data was prepared by converting these scores into percentages, thus facilitating their interpretation. Using R and the ggplot2, dplyr, and readr libraries, we calculated the density of these percentages and generated a density graph. The latter illustrates the distribution of collaboration scores, revealing the variability and trends in interactions between languages.

Identifying transition zones and adjusting collaboration thresholds

We paid particular attention to identifying dips in this distribution, which mark less frequent collaboration scores. These points were highlighted on the graph, accompanied by annotations to facilitate their interpretation. This analysis made it possible to determine significant collaboration thresholds, providing an overview of the dynamics of interaction between languages. The collaboration thresholds were adjusted according to the thresholds identified in the analysis of MC between paradigms, refining our understanding of the transitions between different levels of interaction.

Implications of collaboration scores for integration

Analysis of the prevalence of collaboration scores reveals insights into the capacity for integration and synergistic operation between languages, highlighting both the potential for compatibility and the challenges of combining diverse paradigms. High scores indicate strong potential for integration, while low scores highlight limitations to synergy. This study highlights the need for a strategic selection of technologies for the development of software solutions.

Fig. 3: Distribution of MC values between languages

Statistical considerations

The shape of the distribution suggests an asymmetric normal distribution, with a sharp peak towards the centre and a longer tail extending towards the higher collaboration scores. The thresholds represented by the dotted vertical lines identify areas of change in the slope of the curve and could denote distinct categories of collaboration.

- The central area of the distribution, where the density is highest, indicates a level of paradigmatic compatibility common to many languages. It is in this area that the

majority of languages seem to cluster, proposing some tendency towards a common set of paradigmatic features.

- The thresholds identified are inflection points where the frequency of collaboration scores changes more rapidly. These points could signal transitions between compatibility regimes, which could correspond to the significant cross-paradigmatic collaboration thresholds identified earlier.

It is worth noting that, although the graph proposes a gradation of collaboration across languages, the partial absence of distinctly separate clusters raises the question of the uniformity of the distribution of collaboration scores. This could reflect an inherently gradual nature of cross-language collaboration, where clear distinctions between levels of compatibility are less pronounced.

3 Conclusion

This supplementary material, building upon the foundational work presented in our earlier study (Vandeloise et al. 2024), has furthered the development of metrics to assess collaboration across programming paradigms and languages. Through a systematic application of standardized metrics, we have quantitatively analysed the synergy among 28 paradigms and identified significant potential for productive interactions in 378 paradigm combinations.

Adjustments to metric parameters have enhanced neutrality and allowed for the customization of analytical tools to meet specific research needs, thereby increasing the practical utility of our methodologies. The Haskell-based modelling and the availability of both cleaned and raw datasets ensure comprehensive support for diverse analytical pursuits, promoting an extensive examination of collaborative dynamics.

This work provides a robust framework for evaluating and enhancing the interoperability of programming paradigms and languages, thereby contributing significantly to the field of software engineering research. Future studies may build on this framework to explore more granular interactions and refine the metrics for broader applicability.

References

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